
Exploring community governance models

Introduction

We created this worksheet for our November 2021 community call on community governance models. Several members of our community of practice had voiced a need for a conversation on this topic, and so to facilitate that conversation we used the [Community Rules eBook](#) as a guide and created the worksheets included here to get the discussion going. We found that this activity sparked some interesting conversations, highlighted nuance in the various models, and helped us all understand the complexities and power structures at play in our own communities.

How a community is run is crucial to its success. Governance structures can influence member engagement, the ability of a community to achieve its goals, and the perception of a community in a larger ecosystem. Reflecting on the structure in place in your own community can also shine a light on potential pain points or situations of inequity and exclusion. We hope that you find this document helpful as you host your own conversations on community governance.

Instructions

This activity is based on models outlined in [Community Rule](#) under a CC BY-SA license. Note: we chose five of the eight models in the book when creating these worksheets, those which seemed most relevant to the communities in our ecosystem.

- The worksheets below are intended to promote discussion of five models of community governance. From our experience, a group size of 4-6 is optimal. If you are a small group, you might use the worksheets in sequential meetings, or for larger groups, breakout groups can take one model each.
- During the discussion, ensure that at least one person is taking notes. This will help for breakout reporting, as well as sharing knowledge among others in a larger group.
- If you are hosting a subsequent report-out, ensure that one person in each group knows that they are responsible for doing so. The reporter should try to synthesize a few key learnings for the larger group, rather than sharing a long list of details.
- Note: the prompts are intended to promote conversation. Depending on how long you have for this activity, you may or may not get through them all.

Worksheets

WORKSHEET 1: BENEVOLENT DICTATOR

“The benevolent dictator holds ultimate decision-making power, until the group is ready for a more inclusive structure.” - [Community Rule](#)

Values: servant leadership, singular vision, voluntarism

Discussion prompts:

- **When or why might this model be implemented?** E.g., as a community is first established, leaders self-identify and take on the tasks of building documentation.
- **What are the main benefits / most attractive features of using this model?** E.g., it has defined opportunities for community members to voice their concerns.
- **Can you think of an organization either within your group or within the STEM ecosystem that uses this model?** E.g., CSCCE implements multiple models of governance depending on circumstances, goals, and feedback from community members.
- **What are the major challenges for implementing this model?** E.g., reaching consensus, scheduling regular meetings, maintaining coherent brand identity.
- **What kind of power structure or imbalances might play out in this model?** E.g., this model might deter members from suggesting specific consensus-based member-led activities because they might assume that they are not welcome to do so.
- **How might this model interplay with other governance models?** E.g., there may exist subgroups that use their own governance models such as consensus that enable members to decide together on actions.

WORKSHEET 2: DO-OCRACY

“Those who take initiative to do something in the group can decide how they do it.” - [Community Rule](#)

Values: bias for action, consultation, decentralization

Discussion prompts:

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- **Can you think of an organization either within your group or within the STEM ecosystem that uses this model?** E.g., CSCCE implements multiple models of governance depending on circumstances, goals, and feedback from community members.
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- **What kind of power structure or imbalances might play out in this model?** E.g., this model might deter members from suggesting specific consensus-based member-led activities because they might assume that they are not welcome to do so.
- **How might this model interplay with other governance models?** E.g., there may exist subgroups that use their own governance models such as consensus that enable members to decide together on actions.

WORKSHEET 3: JURY

“Proposals are shaped and decided on by randomly selected juries.” -

[Community Rule](#)

Values: equality, participation, study

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- **Can you think of an organization either within your group or within the STEM ecosystem that uses this model?** E.g., CSCCE implements multiple models of governance depending on circumstances, goals, and feedback from community members.
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WORKSHEET 4: CONSENSUS

“Decisions that affect the group collectively should involve participation of all participants.” - [Community Rule](#)

Values: creativity, empathy, solidarity

Discussion prompts:

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WORKSHEET 5: ELECTED BOARD

“An elected board determines policies and organizes their implementation.”

- [Community Rule](#)

Values: delegation, representation, servant leadership

Discussion prompts:

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- **What are the main benefits / most attractive features of using this model?** E.g., it has defined opportunities for community members to voice their concerns.
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Reference

[Community Rules: Simple Templates for Great Communities.](#) (2021). Cassandra Dana, Drew Hornbein, Vincent Russell, and Nathan Schneider

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CSCCE uses the CREDiT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

ALYCIA CRALL - Conceptualization, Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

KATIE PRATT - Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

LOU WOODLEY - Conceptualization, Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

All three authors contributed equally to the intellectual content of this document, and so are listed alphabetically.

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